

Publishing and analysing open archaeological data is crucial for sustainable urban planning and cultural heritage management.

The Jupyter Python Minion offers an open-source approach to streamline Linked Open Data (LOD) workflows.

The Jupyter Python Minion simplifies complex tasks like SPARQL querying and data visualisation.

By making these workflows shareable and reproducible, the Minion aligns with open science principles and bridges the gap between computational methods and domain expertise.

The tool's geospatial visualisations and linked data integration support urban archaeological potential assessments, offering urban planners, archaeologists, and researchers a transparent framework to assess and safeguard buried heritage in cities like Rome.

However, how to start?

Pokémon Wikidata

Start with Pokémon to query Wikidata

Let's play with Pokémon on Wikidata

✓ Pokémon Color Distribution Visualization

This notebook fetches Pokémon data using a SPARQL query from Wikidata and creates a bar chart showing the distribution of Pokémon by color. The bars are colored according to the Pokémon colors, and white bars have a distinct black border for better visibility.

```
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']
```

[5]

✓ 0.0s

Python

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-pokemon-colour>

Starting with setting up the SPARQL query against Wikidata ...

Define the SPARQL Query

```
pokemonQuery = """
SELECT DISTINCT ?pokemon ?pokemonLabel ?pokedexNumber ?color ?colorLabel
WHERE
{
    ?pokemon wdt:P31/wdt:P279* wd:Q3966183 .
    ?pokemon p:P1685 ?statement.
    ?pokemon wdt:P462 ?color.
    ?statement ps:P1685 ?pokedexNumber;
    pq:P972 wd:Q20005020.
    FILTER ( !isBLANK(?pokedexNumber) ) .
    SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" }
}
ORDER BY (?pokedexNumber)
"""
```

[6]

✓ 0.0s

Python

... defining the SPARQL query ...

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(pokemonQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    data.append({
        "pokemon": result['pokemon']['value'],
        "pokemonLabel": result['pokemonLabel']['value'],
        "pokedexNumber": int(result['pokedexNumber']['value']),
        "color": result['color']['value'],
        "colorLabel": result['colorLabel']['value'],
    })

# Create a DataFrame
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

[7]

✓ 2.0s

Python

		pokemon	pokemonLabel	pokedexNumber		color	colorLabel
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q847571	Bulbasaur		1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1636903	Ivysaur		2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2283930	Venusaur		3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3178753	Charmander		4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3142	red	
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1637365	Chameleon		5	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3142	red	
...
992	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116699173	Iron Thorns		995	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	
993	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116699174	Frigibax		996	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q42519	grey	
994	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116699175	Arctibax		997	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q42519	grey	
995	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116699177	Baxcalibur		998	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q42519	grey	
996	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q115117784	Gimmighoul		999	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q47071	brown	

997 rows × 5 columns

... convert the results into a DataFrame ...

Visualize the Data with a Bar Chart

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Bar chart: Count Pokémon by color
    color_counts = df['colorLabel'].value_counts()

    # Map color labels to actual colors
    color_mapping = {
        "red": "red",
        "blue": "blue",
        "green": "green",
        "yellow": "yellow",
        "purple": "purple",
        "pink": "pink",
        "brown": "brown",
        "white": "white",
        "black": "black",
        "gray": "gray",
    }

    # Create a list of bar colors based on the color labels
    bar_colors = [color_mapping.get(color.lower(), "gray") for color in color_counts.index]
```

```
# Plot the bar chart with black edges
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
bars = plt.bar(
    color_counts.index,
    color_counts.values,
    color=bar_colors,
    edgecolor="black", # Add black border
    linewidth=1.5     # Adjust border thickness
)

# Customize the white bar to ensure visibility
for bar, color in zip(bars, bar_colors):
    if color == "white":
        bar.set_edgecolor("black")
        bar.set_linewidth(2)

plt.title("Distribution of Pokémon by Color")
plt.xlabel("Color")
plt.ylabel("Number of Pokémon")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

0.2s

Python

... choose a visualisation method ...

... to create a colour distribution bar chart of Pokémons ...

```

pokemonQuery = """
SELECT DISTINCT ?pokemon ?pokemonLabel ?pokedexNumber ?color ?colorLabel ?mass
WHERE
{
  ?pokemon wdt:P31/wdt:P279* wd:Q3966183 .
  ?pokemon p:P1685 ?statement.
  ?pokemon wdt:P462 ?color.
  ?pokemon wdt:P2067 ?mass.
  ?statement ps:P1685 ?pokedexNumber;
  | pq:P972 wd:Q20005020.
  FILTER ( !isBLANK(?pokedexNumber) ) .
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" }
}
ORDER BY (?pokedexNumber)
"""

```

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-pokemon-mass>

	pokemon	pokemonLabel	pokedexNumber	color	colorLabel	mass
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q847571	Bulbasaur	1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	6.9
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q847571	Bulbasaur	1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	15.2
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1636903	Ivysaur	2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	13.0
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2283930	Venusaur	3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3133	green	100.0
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3178753	Charmander	4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3142	red	8.5
...
533	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q115731520	Clodsire	980	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q47071	brown	491.6
534	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116698220	Kingambit	983	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23445	black	120.0
535	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q116698220	Kingambit	983	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q23445	black	264.6
536	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q115117784	Gimmighoul	999	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q47071	brown	0.1
537	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q115117784	Gimmighoul	999	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q47071	brown	5.0

538 rows × 6 columns

... or by adding the mass ...

Scatter Plot: Yellow Pokémon Mass vs. Pokémon

... creating a scatter plot.

Ogham Sites

... in Wikidata to create diagrams and maps.

Let's play with Ogham Data on Wikidata

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
"""
```

	item	itemLabel	geo	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69377850	CIIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-8.818333 52.015833)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69378412	Barrahaurn (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69377850	CIIC 103 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-8.4924431 51.8936593)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69378412	Barrahaurn (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69383434	CIIC 115 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-8.794722 51.868056)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69383268	Knockshanawee (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69383434	CIIC 115 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-8.4922616 51.8937168)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69383268	Knockshanawee (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69385241	CIIC 117 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-8.794722 51.868056)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q69383268	Knockshanawee (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry
333	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	Point(-10.031111 52.1725)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry

334 rows x 7 columns

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "geo": result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None,
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

```

# Define a color palette for counties
unique_counties = df['countyLabel'].unique()
county_colors = {county: color for county, color in zip(unique_counties, plt.cm.tab20.colors)}

# Group by county and site to count stones
site_counts = df.groupby(['countyLabel', 'siteLabel']).size().reset_index(name='count')

# Identify the top 3 sites per county
top_sites = site_counts.groupby('countyLabel').apply(lambda x: x.nlargest(3, 'count')).reset_index(drop=True)

```

```

# Create a bar plot for the top 3 sites per county
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
for county, group in top_sites.groupby('countyLabel'):
    plt.bar(group['siteLabel'], group['count'], color=county_colors[county], label=county)

```

```

plt.title("Top 3 Sites per County with the Most Ogham Stones")
plt.xlabel("Sites")
plt.ylabel("Number of Ogham Stones")
plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
plt.legend(title="County", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

```

# Bar plot: Distribution by counties
county_counts = df['countyLabel'].value_counts()
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))
county_counts.plot(kind='bar', color=[county_colors[county] for county in county_counts.index])
plt.title("Distribution of Ogham Stones by Counties")
plt.xlabel("Counties")
plt.ylabel("Number of Ogham Stones")
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Create Charts

Top 2 Sites per County with the Most Ogham Stones

- County Carlow
- County Cavan
- County Clare
- County Cork
- County Donegal
- County Galway
- County Kerry
- County Kildare
- County Kilkenny
- County Leitrim
- County Limerick
- County Louth
- County Mayo
- County Meath
- County Roscommon
- County Waterford
- County Wexford
- County Wicklow

Distribution of Ogham Stones by Counties

Charts Output

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q2016147.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617071.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
"""
```

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770633	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows x 8 columns

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()

# Map 3: Density map with normalized values
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Calculate kernel density
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)

# Normalize density to range [0, 1]
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Map Output

Samian Ware

... in Wikidata to create diagrams.

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALLE

Let's play with Samian Ware Data on Wikidata

https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata_samian_kilnsites

```
# SPARQL Query for Samian Ware Kiln Sites
samianQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geo ?layerLabel ?layer ?kilnregion ?kilnregionLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q102202026;
  wdt:P361 wd:Q90412636;
  wdt:P706 ?kilnregion;
  wdt:P2888 ?samian;
  wdt:P625 ?geo;
  wdt:P706 ?layer.
SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
"""
```

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(samianQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result.get('geo', {}).get('value', None)
    lat, lon = None, None
    if geo:
        coords = geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split()
        if len(coords) == 2:
            lon, lat = map(float, coords)
    data.append({
        "item": result.get("item", {}).get("value", None),
        "itemLabel": result.get("itemLabel", {}).get("value", None),
        "layerLabel": result.get("layerLabel", {}).get("value", None),
        "kilnregionLabel": result.get("kilnregionLabel", {}).get("value", None),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

	item	itemLabel	layerLabel	kilnregionLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136249	Sagone (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	42.112142	8.702547
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136253	Albi (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	43.927186	2.149255
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136256	Rodez (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	44.352370	2.572616
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q102763431	La Graufesenque (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	44.100000	3.083333
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103135455	Banassac (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	South Gaulish (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	44.433333	3.200000
...
98	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136223	Torrita di Siena (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	43.166668	11.766666
99	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136227	Vasanello (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	42.416699	12.350000
100	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136235	Venosa (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	40.966667	15.816667
101	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136239	Micasasa (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	Dacian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	Dacian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	46.086660	24.108056
102	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q103136244	Lyon (Samian Ware Productioncentre)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	Italian (Samian Ware Kilnregion)	45.760000	4.840000

103 rows x 6 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

```

# Count sites by region and layer for stacked bar chart
region_layer_counts = df.groupby(["kilnregionLabel", "layerLabel"]).size().unstack(fill_value=0)

# Create pie chart data
region_counts = df["kilnregionLabel"].value_counts()

# Stacked Bar Chart
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
region_layer_counts.plot(kind="bar", stacked=True, figsize=(12, 8), colormap="tab20")
plt.title("Distribution of Kiln Sites by Region and Layer", fontsize=16)
plt.xlabel("Kiln Region", fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel("Number of Sites", fontsize=14)
plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
plt.legend(title="Layer", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc="upper left")
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

```

# Pie Chart
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 10))
region_counts.plot(kind="pie", autopct="%1.1f%%", startangle=90, colors=plt.cm.Paired.colors)
plt.title("Proportion of Kiln Sites by Region", fontsize=16)
plt.ylabel("") # Remove default ylabel
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Create Charts

Distribution of Kiln Sites by Region and Layer

Proportion of Kiln Sites by Region

Chart Output

Holy Wells

... in Wikidata to create diagrams.

Let's play with Holy Wells Data on Wikidata

```
# SPARQL Query for Holy Wells and Their Etymologies
holyWellsQuery = """
SELECT ?etymology ?etymologyLabel (COUNT(?HW) AS ?count)
WHERE
{
  ?HW wdt:P31 wd:Q126443332.
  ?HW wdt:P131 wd:Q180231.
  ?HW wdt:P138 ?etymology.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
GROUP BY ?etymology ?etymologyLabel
ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

	etymology	etymologyLabel	count
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q345	Mary	23
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2151232	townland	15
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q80979	Brigid of Kildare	11
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q165479	Saint Patrick	10
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2280421	Ciarán of Saigir	10
...
75	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q133704	Martin of Tours	1
76	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q676555	Francis of Assisi	1
77	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q6686215	Loughman	1
78	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q17590	Lawrence of Rome	1
79	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3072671	Fintan	1

80 rows × 3 columns

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(holyWellsQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    data.append({
        "etymology": result['etymology']['value'],
        "etymologyLabel": result['etymologyLabel']['value'],
        "count": int(result['count']['value']),
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-tod/wikidata_holywells_names

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

```

# Generate Word Cloud
wordcloud = WordCloud(width=800, height=400, background_color="white").generate_from_frequencies(
    dict(zip(df["etymologyLabel"], df["count"]))
)

plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
plt.imshow(wordcloud, interpolation="bilinear")
plt.axis("off")
plt.title("Word Cloud of Holy Well Namesakes", fontsize=16)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

```

# Generate Pie Chart with Filtering
df_sorted = df.sort_values(by="count", ascending=False)
total_count = df_sorted["count"].sum()

# Filter namesakes > 1% and group the rest into "Others"
df_sorted["percentage"] = (df_sorted["count"] / total_count) * 100
df_filtered = df_sorted[df_sorted["percentage"] > 1]
others_count = df_sorted[df_sorted["percentage"] <= 1]["count"].sum()

# Add "Others" if applicable
if others_count > 0:
    df_filtered = pd.concat(
        [
            df_filtered,
            pd.DataFrame({"etymologyLabel": ["Others"], "count": [others_count], "percentage": [others_count / total_count * 100]})
        ]
    )

# Pie chart
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
plt.pie(
    df_filtered["count"],
    labels=df_filtered["etymologyLabel"],
    autopct='%1.1f%%',
    startangle=90,
    colors=plt.cm.Paired.colors
)
plt.title("Proportion of Holy Wells by Namesake (>1%)", fontsize=16)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()

```

Create Charts

Word Cloud of Holy Well Namesakes

Proportion of Holy Wells by Namesake (>1%)

Chart Output

Campanian Ignimbrite

... sites in a solid pod to create diagrams / maps.

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALLÉ

Let's play with Campanian Ignimbrite Data through a Solid Pot

```

from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, TURTLE
from rdflib import Graph, Namespace
from rdflib.namespace import RDF, RDFS
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

# Function to query Solid Pod and retrieve data in TURTLE format
def querySolidPod(sparql_endpoint, query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper(sparql_endpoint)
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(TURTLE) # Request Turtle format
    results = sparql.query().convert()
    return results

# SPARQL Query
solid_pod_query = """
SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType {
  ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
  ?item rdfs:label ?label.
  ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
  ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
  ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
  ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
}
"""

```

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/solidpod-ci>

```

sparql_endpoint = "https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl"

# Query the endpoint
turtle_data = querySolidPod(sparql_endpoint, solid_pod_query)

# Parse Turtle data with rdflib
g = Graph()
g.parse(data=turtle_data, format="turtle")

# Extract namespaces
site_ns = Namespace("http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/")
gs = Namespace("http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#")

# Run the SPARQL query against the loaded Turtle data
results = g.query(solid_pod_query)

# Process the Results into a DataFrame
data = []
for row in results:
    spatial_type = str(row.spatialType).replace("http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/", "")
    geo_str = str(row.geo)
    if geo_str.find("POINT(") != -1:
        geo_str = geo_str.replace("<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>", "").replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "")
    else:
        geo_str = geo_str.replace("<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSSG/0/4326>", "")
        geo_str = geo_str.replace(")", "")
        geo_str = geo_str.replace(" POINT (", "")

    lon, lat = map(float, geo_str.split())

    data.append({
        "spatialType": spatial_type,
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

# Convert the data to a pandas DataFrame
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df

```

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

	spatialType	latitude	longitude
0	Sink	40.9489	14.3624
1	UnknownCategory	40.9285	14.6983
2	InhabitedPlace	40.7119	14.7680
3	InhabitedPlace	40.6993	14.5259
4	Cave	40.4956	15.2092
...
98	UnknownCategory	44.9032	20.2802
99	UnknownCategory	44.2462	27.9347
100	UnknownCategory	44.2462	27.9347
101	Lake	40.9167	21.0000
102	Lake	40.9167	21.0000

103 rows × 3 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

```

# Check if DataFrame is populated
if not df.empty and 'spatialType' in df:
    # Plot 1: Number of Sites by Spatial Type
    plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
    df['spatialType'].value_counts().plot(kind='bar', color='skyblue', edgecolor='black')
    plt.title("Number of Sites by Spatial Type", fontsize=16)
    plt.xlabel("Spatial Type", fontsize=14)
    plt.ylabel("Number of Sites", fontsize=14)
    plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.show()
else:
    print("No data retrieved or 'spatialType' column is missing.")

```

```

# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Plot points on the map
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="CI sites")

    # Add OSM basemap
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik)

    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of CI sites in Europe")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

```

Create Chart & Map

Map of CI sites in Europe

Output Chart & Map

Analyse Roman Sites

... from Wikidata

Let's play with "Roman Data" on Wikidata

```

1 #Archaeological Sites in Italy
2 #defaultView:Map
3 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
4   ?item (wdt:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q839954.
5   ?item wdt:P17 wd:Q38.
6   ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
7   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img }
8   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
9 }

```


<https://w.wiki/CTDH>

Archaeological Sites in Italy in Wikidata

```
# SPARQL Query
sitesQuery = """
SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
  ?item (wdt:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q839954.
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q19757.
  ?item wdt:P17 wd:Q38.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img }
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
"""
```

	item	itemLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28001156	Roman theatre of Helvia Recina	43.327540	13.421620
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q108538145	Theatrum Scauri	41.897778	12.477222
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28001184	Roman Theatre of Urbisaglia	43.198883	13.380765
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q30524161	Roman Theatre of Terracina	41.291750	13.248869
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q130634552	Roman theater at Castrum Novum	42.037480	11.833034
...
77	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q21196047	theatre of Nuceria Alfaterna	40.737840	14.662740
78	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q53673000	Roman Theatre of Falerio Picenus	43.102452	13.499982
79	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q123154036	Roman Theatre of Saepinum	41.434440	14.617480
80	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q100273162	Roman theater in Ocriculum	42.415380	12.465270
81	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70863776	ancient Roman theater of Cales	41.199925	14.132109

82 rows × 4 columns

Map of Roman theatres in Italy

Archaeological Sites in Italy in Wikidata (Roman theatres)

```
# SPARQL Query
sitesQuery = """
SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
  ?item (wdt:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q839954.
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q172896.
  ?item wdt:P17 wd:Q38.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img }
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
}
"""
```

	item	itemLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q112661376	Catacombe del Mulinello	37.236900	15.173755
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663207	Catacomb of San Zotico	41.850465	12.667922
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q546419	Catacombs of San Sebastiano	41.855762	12.516484
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663192	Catacomb of Commodilla	41.861167	12.483472
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663174	Catacomb of San Castulo	41.886014	12.525928
5	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663177	Catacombe di San Lorenzo	41.902818	12.521068
6	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663175	Catacomb of San Nicomede	41.910889	12.507861
7	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663191	Cataomba maggiore	41.922781	12.518611
8	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663182	Catacombs of Saint Agnes	41.922778	12.518611
9	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1027069	Catacomb of Callixtus	41.858878	12.511058
10	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1255593	Q1255593	40.833333	14.250000
11	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1256347	Q1256347	40.833333	14.250000
12	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663214	Vigna Randanini	41.856800	12.518500
13	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663173	Catacomb of Calepodius	41.892580	12.432400
14	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1055805	Catacombs of Marcellinus and Peter	41.879028	12.549083
15	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663181	Catacomb of Sant'Ermete	41.923025	12.488319
16	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663204	San Senatore catacombs	41.723117	12.663904
17	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663213	Catacombs in Syracuse	37.076944	15.285556
18	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663215	Catacomb of Via Anapo	41.926400	12.506200
19	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663166	Catacomb dei Santi Processo e Martiniano	41.886742	12.456312
20	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3801612	Hypogeum of Vibia	41.861900	12.510200
21	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3663210	Catacombs di Santa Felicità	41.917869	12.497285

Map of catacombs in Italy

Archaeological Sites in Italy in Wikidata (catacombs)

```

1 #Archaeological Sites in Chieti, Italy
2 #defaultView:Map
3 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
4   ?item (wdt:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q839954.
5   ?item wdt:P17 wd:Q38.
6   ?item wdt:P131 wd:Q13138.
7   ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
8   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img }
9   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
10 }

```


Archaeological Sites in Chieti (Italy) in Wikidata

```
# SPARQL Query
sitesQuery = """
SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?img WHERE {
  ?item (wdt:P31/(wdt:P279*)) wd:Q839954.
  ?item wdt:P17 wd:Q38.
  ?item wdt:P131 wd:Q13138.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img }
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
}
"""
```


	item	itemLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q55685833	Chieti Roman theatre	42.347124	14.163451
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3554226	Teate	42.346992	14.168101
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q28978015	Teate Marrucinorum amphitheatre	42.345025	14.162539
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q3867665	Archeological Museum La Civitella	42.345096	14.162026

Archaeological Sites in Chieti (Italy) in Wikidata

Conclusio

The Python Jupyter Minion works!

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALLÉ

Enjoy christmas | Godetevi il Natale

Finis! Grazie! Questions?

Florian Thiery M.Sc.
Research Squirrel Engineers Network
mail@fthiery.de
ORCID: 0000-0002-3246-3531

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